

MONITORING FEEDSTOCK LOSSES OVER 6 MONTHS STORAGE OF OLIVE TREE PRUNING HOG FUEL IN PILES. COMPARISON OF PILES WITH OR WITHOUT COVERAGE

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ABSTRACT: Aim of the current paper is the monitoring of feedstock losses during the six months storage of harvested olive tree prunings (OTP), by comparing two storage solutions: i) uncovered, open-air storage and ii) covered storage. For this task, two identical conical piles of harvested prunings were built and monitored for calculating the changes in dry matter and energy content of the stored material over time. One pile was built as-is and the other was covered with a fleece. For each pile, sample bags were used in order to monitor the alterations in dry matter and energy content of the stored OTP. In overall, the covered pile showed greater storage performance than the uncovered pile, where the latter depended mostly on weather conditions. The covered pile presented lower dry matter losses after 6 months of storage (average value of 1.1 % compared to 4.6 % of the uncovered pile), stable moisture content throughout the storage period (around 10 % compared to fluctuating moisture content of uncovered pile from 11 % to 21 %), that also resulted in energy content gain (average pile value of energy content gain of 12.1 % compared to energy content loss of 5.1 % of the uncovered pile).

Keywords: biomass, olive tree, agricultural residues, storage, monitoring

1 INTRODUCTION

Olive tree groves are a characteristic crop of the Mediterranean basin that generate substantial amounts of residual biomass. Mostly once or twice every year, pruning of olive trees is performed to maintain the health of the trees. Prunings (branches and shoots of fruit trees with less than 5 cm diameter) produced from the Southern European Countries amount to around 5.5 Million dry tons [1]. Olive tree prunings (OTP) represent an abundant source of energy biomass, or raw material for added value products, still largely unexploited.

Until now, the management of pruning residue has generally represented a disposal problem, rather than an opportunity for additional revenue. Prunings are either mulched, or in the majority of cases, piled and burned in open-fires. The first method may lead to phytopathological issues, whereas the latter has negative environmental impact and possess a risk related to fire hazards.

However, prunings can be exploited in various ways such as solid biofuels in chip or pellet form for heating applications or as feedstock in power plants [2-3]. In addition, they can also be used as feedstock for the production of bio commodities (e.g. particleboard by replacing common wood, bioethanol, paper etc.) [4]. In this light, due to the seasonal availability of OTP, the storage of such biomass is an essential process step towards the successful implementation of a bioenergy value chain, that would secure the annual supply of OTP throughout the year.

In general, during storage of wet biomass (chips or hog fuel), the growth of different fungi is enhanced, heating up the pile up to 80°C or even more. The majority of isolated fungi are mold fungi which degrade available soluble sugars. However, some species are able to metabolize cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin causing economical relevant losses of biomass. Beside water content, particle size, height and shape of woodchip piles are important factors that have to be considered. Woodchips with a small particle size offer a higher surface to be colonized by fungi. In addition, a high sawdust and

fine material content (e.g. needles or leaves) causes limited air passage leading to higher temperatures [5]. In this sense, storage of OTP is a very important factor for the realization of a bioenergy value chain. Thus, monitoring of feedstock losses during OTP storage was performed, in order to optimize the storage strategy and investigate how the OTP's quality is affected.

Finally, the outcome of the present paper is the detailed monitoring of the feedstock losses during 6 months of storage. The goal is to evaluate the storage behavior of the harvested olive tree prunings via the comparison of two different storage configurations, with or without coverage, and the impact of long storage onto the properties of OTP in terms of changes in moisture content, dry matter losses and energy content.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Harvesting of olive tree prunings

The olive prunings were harvested by mechanized means (integrated harvester/ mulcher) in Agios Konstantinos, Central Greece [6]. Olive tree prunings that are subjected to harvesting are thin branches (branches and shoots) which are previously separated from thick branches (over 5 cm diameter). The latter are collected from farmers to be used as firewood. After the alignment of OTP on the field, the integrated harvester goes over the rows of prunings and harvests them by shredding OTP into small and inhomogeneous pieces (Figure 1). The shredded material has an inhomogeneous character and its particle size varies, with over 75% of the harvested OTP to have a particle size between 45 mm to less than 3.15 mm.

Figure 1: Harvested olive tree prunings

2.2 Construction of piles

Two almost identical piles were built: i) one pile as-is (pile A), without any coverage and ii) one pile covered with a Flortex® 55/300 (Edilfloor) fleece (pile B). The special fleece is a green polypropylene nonwoven of 300 g/m², UV rays treated, breathable, wind resistant, hydrophobic fabric that is specifically designed for compost maturation and woodchips protection. Each pile had a height of 3 m and a diameter of 5.5 m. For the construction of each pile around 10 wet tons of harvested OTP were used. Each pile was divided in 4 layers with each of the three layers at 1m height. A fourth layer is actually the top of the pile. In each pile, 4 thermocouples (Pt 100) were used in order to measure the temperatures variations inside each pile in four different spots. Three sensors were inserted in the middle of the pile at 0.5 m, 1.5 m and 2.5 m from the ground. Different “depths” of the pile were used in order to investigate the impact of the different position in the pile. A fourth thermocouple was inserted at the side of the pile in the second layer (1.5 m from the ground), at 1.5 m from the center of the pile. The cables used with the thermocouples had a length of 10 m and had Teflon as cable insulation. All eight thermocouples were connected to a data logger located between the two piles in order to record the temperatures inside both piles. The data logger used is a Delta OHM HD 32.7 data logger with 8 inputs. Temperature was recorded every 10 minutes. The major part of the cable was inserted into a metal pipe as an extra outer protection of the cable from the weight of the pile.

In each pile, apart from the thermocouples, sample bags (

Figure 2: Breathable sample bag used to measure the weight loss of stored material over the storage period) were used. The sample bags were filled with harvested OTP in order to measure the weight variations of the feedstock over the storage period. Breathable sample bags with mesh were used in order for the material stored inside not get influenced from the sample bag.

Figure 2: Breathable sample bag used to measure the weight loss of stored material over the storage period

During the construction phase of the piles (Figure 3), after the completion of each layer, sample bags were inserted before continuing the construction of the rest pile. In each layer, various subsamples from different spots

of the layer were retrieved for fuel analyses. For the first three layers 6 subsamples were collected from each layer, whereas in the fourth one two subsamples were retrieved. Thus, for each pile 4 samples from all layers were collected for fuel analyses. Continuously, apart from collecting samples of each layer, sample bags were filled with harvested OTP and were inserted at different spots of each layer. Sample bags were weighted prior to their allocation on each layer. Furthermore, another sample of OTP was collected from every spot where the material was used to fill the sample bags for fuel analyses. In this light, the determination of the initial properties of the OTP (e.g. moisture, heating and ash content etc.) was performed, in order compare them with the fuel properties of OTP in the sample bags after the end of the storage period.

Figure 3: Construction of piles of OTP for monitoring feedstock losses during storage

Sample bags were inserted at the thermocouples’ positions and also in other spots in each layer, as can be seen in the following drawing (Figure 4). Moreover, in the one side of each pile, three sample bags were allocated at the same spot of each of the first three layers. In this light, every two months, that side of each pile would be opened and one sample bag from each layer would be retrieved. In this sense, the impact on the properties of stored material every two months would be investigated. After retrieving the sample bags, the part of pile opened is put back again. Finally, apart from the filled sample bags, three empty “blind” sample bags were also allocated inside each pile. One blind bag per pile was retrieved every two months of storage in order to correct the final results by taking into account the mass change of the bags.

Figure 4: Pile A (without coverage) and pile B (with fleece): construction data and position of thermocouples and sample bags

Figure 5: Constructed piles. Right: Pile A, without fleece; Left: Pile B, with fleece

In total, each pile had 16 sample bags filled with OTP, 4 thermocouples and 3 “blind” bags. During the construction phase, for each pile 16 samples of material were retrieved from the locations where OTP was used to fill the sample bags along with four samples in total from all layers. After every two months of storage, apart from the sample bags recovered (3 sample bags per pile after every two months and one “blind” bag), one sample per layer was also recovered (3 subsamples per first three layers and 2 subsamples from last layer). In brief, a total of 48 samples per pile were retrieved and analyzed throughout the storage period.

2.3 Fuel analyses of samples and calculation of dry matter losses and energy content variation of stored OTP

In October, after 6 months of storage, all sample bags were recovered along with the thermocouples and the data recorded from the data logger. Sample bags were weighted again after the storage period and then sent for fuel analyses.

Throughout the whole storage period, in total 96 samples of OTP were sent to CErTH’s laboratories for analyses regarding the characterization of fuel properties. The fuel characterization was performed in CErTH/CPERI’s laboratories in Ptolemaida by applying established standards (EN 14774 for moisture, EN 14775 for ash, EN 14918 for heating value, EN 15104 for ultimate analysis).

After receiving the fuel analyses of samples during the construction of the piles and after a storage period of 2, 4 and 6 months, several parameters were calculated.

Indicatively, the dry matter losses, for these storage periods, were calculated as the percentage reduction of the dry weight during storage, following equation (eq. 1):

$$DML_i = \left[1 - \left(\frac{DM_i}{DM_{in}} \right) \right] \times 100 \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

Where:

- DML: Dry matter losses (% , dry basis)
- DM_{in}: Dry weight at storage start (kg, dry basis)
- DM_i: Dry weight after storage at time i (kg, dry basis, with i: 2, 4 and 6 months)

Apart from the dry matter changes, the variations in the energy content of the stored olive tree prunings was calculated by taking into consideration dry matter losses, changes in moisture content, and changes in heating values, following the equation (eq. 2):

$$EV_i = \left[\left(\left(1 - \frac{DML_i}{100} \right) \times LHV_i \right) - LHV_{in} \right] \times \frac{100}{LHV_{in}} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

Where:

- EV_i: energy change after storage at time i (% , as received, with i: 2, 4 and 6 months)

DML_i: Dry matter losses after storage at time i (% , dry basis)

LHV_{in}: Lower heating value on wet basis at storage start (MJ/kg, as received)

LHV_i: Lower heating value on wet basis after storage time i (MJ/kg, as received, with i: 2, 4 and 6 months)

3 RESULTS

After six months of storage, the piles were dismantled and all sample bags and thermocouples were recovered. The sample bags were firstly weighted and then sent to CErTH’s laboratories for analysis.

3.1 Weather conditions and temperature profiles of piles

The temperature profile inside the piles is depicted in Figure 6. The data logger recorded temperatures from 15/05/19 to 22/10/19 (storage period). Every 10 minutes, the data logger recorded the temperatures inside the piles. Furthermore,

Figure 6 presents the weather conditions as retrieved from a nearby meteorological station.

Figure 7 presents the weather conditions and the average temperature of each pile during the whole storage period.

Figure 6: Weather conditions and temperatures inside the piles during storage

Figure 7: Weather conditions and temperatures inside the piles during storage; Average temperatures of each pile

The storage period May- October, was characterized by a dry and warm weather. Precipitation amounted up to a total of 60.4 mm in the storage area. Mean air temperature was 24.4 °C, with a minimum temperature of 16.3 °C and a maximum temperature of 39.3 °C. The average wind speed was at 6.6 km/hr with a direction, in

the majority of days, to the North.

Temperatures increased in both piles during the initial period of storage, with a marked raise over the first few days from pile building. After the initial rise, the temperature inside all piles dropped and then remained at a similar level. Interesting is the fact that, some days before the first partial dismantling of the piles (on 19/07, after two months of storage), the average temperature of pile A made a violent peak and raised its temperature. Probably, this is due to the fact that the previous days of the sampling day, there was a high rainfall, thus affecting the uncovered pile A and enhancing the activity of fungi.

In overall, the maximum temperature was recorded for pile B at 51.0 °C, whereas for pile A the maximum temperature was recorded at 47.3 °C. Regarding the minimum recorded temperatures, that was 20.0 °C for pile A and 23.9 °C for pile B. From the temperature trend lines, it can be derived that the temperatures inside pile A had greater fluctuations than pile B where the recorded temperatures were more stable with “non-violent” fluctuations. Thus, this shows that the pile with the fleece showed more stable increases and decreases in temperature, whereas the temperature inside pile A was mostly in direct correlation with the air temperature and weather conditions.

Apart from the fact that the temperature inside pile B was more stable than in pile A (Figure 7), it can be also seen that the average temperature of pile B is higher than pile A. The average temperature inside pile A, from all four thermocouples is at 32.7 °C, whereas that of pile B at 36.1 °C. This shows that the fleece helps the pile to sustain a more stable temperature inside it with not many fluctuations, affected from weather conditions. Whereas, pile A seems to be more dependent on weather conditions with more severe temperature increases and decreases. The higher temperatures in pile B, along with the coverage of the fleece, seems to result to a drier material.

3.2 Quality of OTP after storage trials

Figure 8 presents the piles during the dismantling phase after 6 months of storage. The difference of the material is clear between the two piles. The OTP from pile A, without coverage, has a more dark color from the OTP of pile B (with fleece). The material of pile B was drier than that of pile A. On the contrary, OTP from pile A seem more “decomposed” due to the direct contact with the weather conditions, unlike pile B.

The OTP of pile B, seem to be in a lot better state than those of pile A. The fleece, as it can be seen, has kept away the rain and protected the stored biomass. This can be further justified from

Figure 9. The recovered sample bag from pile A is damaged from water, whereas the sample bags from pile B have no damages. As a result, the fleece protected the inside biomass from outer weather conditions and favored their storage conditions.

Figure 8: Dismantling of piles. Right: Pile A (without coverage); Left: Pile B (with fleece)

Figure 9: Retrieved sample bags after 6 months of storage. Right: Sample bag retrieved from Pile A (without coverage); Left: Sample bag retrieved from Pile B (with fleece).

3.3 Impact of storage on OTP fuel properties

The results from the fuel analyses of the collected samples were used for the determination of moisture content, ash content and energy content variations of the olive tree prunings over the storage period of 2, 4 and 6 months.

Figure 10 and

Figure 11 present several fuel properties of each sample of OTP recovered from each pile. The properties are presented for each point in the pile where sample bags were allocated. In this light, the variations of the quality of stored material, based on the location in the pile, can be observed.

Figure 10 presents the moisture content of each sample across all four layers of both piles. For each sample bag used at each location, a sample was recovered from the bag’s location during the construction phase to determine the initial fuel properties. For each point, the moisture content of the stored material at the start of storage (upper value) and after storage (bottom value) is presented in the following figure. Green values show the moisture content of the material prior to storage and after the storage of two months (19/07/2019 first sampling, after two months storage), whereas the red values show the moisture content of the OTP material after the storage of four months (04/09/2019 second sampling, after four months storage). Finally, the rest values describe the initial moisture content and the final moisture content of the stored OTP after six months of storage.

In pile A, the moisture content of each sample bag is in direct correlation with the weather conditions. After two months of storage, the sample bags retrieved had increased moisture content due to the fact that it was raining the days before the sampling. However, after four months (summer time), the moisture content of the retrieved sample bags had lower moisture content from the initial ones. Finally, after 6 months of storage, the collected sample bags had a slight decrease in their initial moisture content (5.7 % decrease in moisture content after 6 months of storage). It can be also seen, that the smallest variations in moisture content were observed in the top layers in pile A. In layer 3, the average moisture content after six months had the less variation (slightly increased moisture content compared to the other layers that they decreased their moisture content).

On the other hand, pile B (covered pile) presented a steady moisture content decrease in all sample bags after two, four and six months, independently of the weather conditions. More specifically, the samples that were

collected after six months had decreased their moisture content by an average of 44.5 % from their initial moisture. All locations in the covered pile had a uniform trend in reducing their moisture content. It can be noted, that only sample bags in layer 3 (high layer in the pile) had greater decreases in moisture content than the rest layers (average decrease in moisture content of all samples bags of layer 3 at 53.5 % compared to 42.9 % of layer 2 and 38.1 % of layer 1).

Figure 10: Results of fuel analyses of all retrieved sample bags (16 sample bags per pile). Top Value: Moisture Content (% , as received) during construction phase of each pile; Bottom Value: Moisture Content (% , as received) after 2 months (green values), 4 months (red values) and 6 months of storage (black values).

Figure 11 presents the variations of the stored material in dry matter and energy content for different locations of the piles. In the same logic as before, the upper value in the graph presents the dry matter losses at each location, whereas the bottom value presents the variation of the stored material in energy content, as described in equation 2.

In general, the actual usable energy in a fuel is often referred to as the net heating value (or low heating value LHV). The variation in moisture content in the biomass affects its LHV, and therefore storage can have a significant impact on such value. Furthermore, a change in calorific value occurs when the different wood components do not decompose according to their specific calorific values. For example, lignin has a distinctly higher calorific value than cellulose [7], but usually decomposes at a lower rate than hemicellulose and cellulose. Overall, the energy quality of biomass is not uniform and can be positively or negatively affected by storage depending on the duration and conditions of the storage trial. Reduction of moisture is obviously a positive change which increases the material's LHV, increase its energy density, and hence reduce the unit energy cost for transportation. In this sense, storage monitoring can play an important role in the realization of biomass value chains.

Based on Figure 11, the uncovered pile A had greater dry matter losses than pile B (average pile value of 3.7 % compared to 1.5 % of pile B, based on all collected sample bags throughout the storage period) and greater energy losses (-2.3 % compared to energy gain of pile B at 11.6 %).

Furthermore, based on the fuel results, the dry matter losses in pile A were higher for the sample bags found in the bottom layer (layer 1), and also higher after six months of storage compared to two or four months of storage. Regarding, the energy content variation in pile A, higher energy losses were recorded in the higher layers (layer 3). However, this is also in direct correlation with the higher moisture content of that layer.

On the other hand, the covered pile B follows a more stable trend in dry matter losses along its different locations in the pile. Slightly increased dry matter losses can be found in layer 3. Regarding the energy variations, pile B shows energy gains after six months of storage. The average value of energy gain seems to be stable along the different layers of pile B.

Figure 11: Results of fuel analyses of all retrieved sample bags (16 sample bags per pile). Top Value: Dry Matter Losses (% , dry basis, positive values show dry matter losses whereas negative values show dry matter gain) after 2 months (green values), 4 months (red values) and 6 months of storage (black values) for each pile; Bottom Value: Energy Content variation (% , as received, positive values show energy gain, whereas negative values show energy losses) after 2 months (green values), 4 months (red values) and 6 months of storage (black values)

Moreover, the following figure presents the average values of moisture content for the different storage periods, along with their standard deviation based on all recovered OTP samples. Both piles, during their construction phase, had around 18.6 % (± 2.6 %) moisture content. After 2 months of storage, the moisture content of pile A (uncovered) was increased to 20.5 % (± 2.9 %), whereas the moisture content of pile B had already decreased to 8.8 % (± 2.1 %). The moisture content of Pile A increased due to the fact that it was raining before the sampling. After 4 months of storage, it can be seen that the moisture content of pile A has decreased to 10.7 % (± 2.8 %), whereas that of pile B was at around 8.3 % (± 2.7 %). The moisture content of pile A had decreased significantly. This is again attributed to the weather conditions during these additional two months of storage. Due to the summer months, implying a dry and hot weather, the moisture content of the uncovered pile decreased, whereas the average moisture content of the covered pile had a very small decrease. Finally, after a storage period of 6 months, the average moisture content of the covered pile (pile A) increased at 17.4 % (± 2.4 %), whereas that of pile B

(covered) had a slight increase as well at around 10.4 % (\pm 1.6 %) moisture content. The high rainfall of these two autumn months resulted to the increase of the moisture content of the uncovered pile. Finally, it can be concluded, that the moisture content of the uncovered pile (pile A) varied according to the weather conditions, whereas the covered pile B followed a more stable trend with its moisture content, independently of the weather conditions. In overall, after 6 months of storage, the uncovered pile A had 6.3 % moisture content losses, whereas the covered pile B had decreased its moisture content by 44.0 %, compared to their initial moisture contents.

Figure 12: Average moisture content (% , as received) and standard deviation of each pile during the storage period. Results from 48 samples of OTP per pile.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The storage of the harvested OTP is a crucial step while scheduling an OTP exploitation value chain. Especially, in concepts where a high amount of biomass is required to be mobilized and supplied throughout the year. The seasonality of OTP harvesting highlights the importance of OTP storage for achieving a successful OTP-based value chain. Aim of the current paper was the evaluation of two different storage solutions (pile of biomass covered with a fleece or non-covered), and their impact on the OTP fuel quality.

In overall, the covered pile recorded a pretty much stable average temperature at 36.1 °C, whereas the uncovered pile recorded more violent temperature fluctuations that resulted to an average temperature of 32.7 °C throughout the storage period. Furthermore, results regarding the quality of the stored olive tree prunings and the impact of storage on the fuel properties were investigated. In brief, the covered pile showed greater storage performance than the uncovered pile, where the latter depended mostly on weather conditions. Moreover, the covered pile presented lower dry matter losses after 6 months of storage (average value of 1.1 % compared to 4.6 % of the uncovered pile) and stable moisture content throughout the storage period (around 10 % compared to fluctuating moisture content of uncovered pile from 11 % - 21 % moisture content as-received). Lastly, the abovementioned parameters also resulted in energy content gain for the covered OTP (average pile value of energy content gain of 12.1 % compared to energy content loss of 5.1 % for the uncovered pile, after six months of storage).

Based on the storage trials, the storage solution with the fleece seems to have positive impact on the stored material with a relatively low cost (2.2 €/ m² or around 20 €/dry ton OTP). However, the trials were performed for six

months. Thus, the storage behavior of the material during the rest six months is questionable. Nonetheless, compared to the outdoor storage with no further cover, the storage solution with the fleece seems to protect the stored biomass from weather phenomena (e.g. rain) and thus, being a promising storage solution for securing the OTP quality and enhancing an OTP-based value chain.

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7 LOGO SPACE

